

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 101:0 A Psalm of David.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 101:1 לְדָוִד מִזְמוֹר חֲסֹד-</p>
<p>Psa. 101:1 I will ^asing of lovingkindness and ¹justice, To You, O LORD, I will sing praises.</p>	<p>וּמִשְׁפָּט אֲשִׁירָה לְךָ יְהוָה אֲזַמְּרָה : ² אֲשַׁכִּילָהּ אֲבַדְרֶךָ תָּמִים מִתִּי תָּבוֹא אֵלַי אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּתָם-לִבִּי בְּקָרֵב בֵּיתִי : ³ לֹא-אֲשִׁית אֶלְנֶגֶד עֵינַי דְּבַר-בְּלִיעַל עֲשֵׂה-סֹטִים שֹׁנְאָתִי לֹא יִדְבֶּק בִּי : ⁴ לִבִּב עֵקֶשׁ יִסּוֹד מִמֶּנִּי רָע לֹא אֲדַע : ⁵ מִלֹּשְׁוֹנֵי [מִלְשֹׁנַי] בִּסְתֵר אֲרַעְהוּ אוֹתוֹ אֲצַמִּית גְּבוּהַ-עֵינַיִם וּרְתַב לִבִּב אֹתוֹ לֹא אוֹכַל : ⁶ עֵינַי אֲבַנְאֲמִנִי- אֶרֶץ לְשֹׁבֵת עַמִּי הַלֵּךְ בְּדַרְךְ תָּמִים הוּא יִשְׁרְתֵנִי : ⁷ לֹא-יֵשֵׁב א בְּקָרֵב בֵּיתִי עֲשֵׂה רַמְיָה דְּבַר שֹׁקְרִים לֹא-יִכּוֹן לִנְגֹד עֵינַי : ⁸ לְבָקָרִים אֲצַמִּית כָּל-רֹשְׁעֵי-אֶרֶץ לְתַכְרִית מְעִיר-יְהוָה כָּל-פְּעֻלֵי אֲוֵן :</p>
<p>² I will ^{1a}give heed to the ^{2b}blameless way. When will You come to me? I will walk within my house in the ^{3b}integrity of my heart.</p>	
<p>³ I will set no ^aworthless thing before my eyes; I hate the ¹work of those who ^bfall away; It shall not fasten its grip on me.</p>	
<p>⁴ A ^aperverse heart shall depart from me; I will know no evil.</p>	
<p>⁵ Whoever secretly ^aslanders his neighbor, him I will ¹destroy; No one who has a ^bhaughty look and an arrogant heart will I endure.</p>	
<p>Psa. 101:6 My eyes shall be upon the faithful of the land, that they may dwell with me; He who walks in a ^{1a}blameless way is the one who will minister to me.</p>	
<p>⁷ He who ^apractices deceit shall not dwell within my house; He who speaks falsehood ^bshall not ¹maintain his position before me.</p>	
<p>⁸ ^aEvery morning I will ^{1b}destroy all the wicked of the land,</p>	

So as to ^c cut off from the ^d city of the LORD all those who do iniquity.	
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References

Psalm 101:1

¹Or *judgment*

^aPs 51:14; 89:1; 145:7

Psalm 101:2

¹Or *behave prudently in*

²Or *way of integrity*

³Or *blamelessness*

^a1 Sam 18:5, 14

^b1 Kin 9:4

Psalm 101:3

¹Or *practice of apostasy*

^aDeut 15:9

^bJosh 23:6; Ps 40:4

Psalm 101:4

^aProv 11:20

Psalm 101:5

¹Or *silence*

^aPs 50:20; Jer 9:4

^bPs 10:4; 18:27; Prov 6:17

Psalm 101:6

¹Or *way of integrity*

^aPs 119:1

Psalm 101:7

¹Lit *be established before my eyes*

^aPs 43:1; 52:2

^bPs 52:4, 5

Psalm 101:8

¹Or *silence*

^aJer 21:12

^bPs 75:10

^cPs 118:10-12

⁴Ps 46:4; 48:2, 8

Targum

Psa. 101:1 Composed by David, a psalm. Whether you show mercy to me or treat me with justice, for both of them I will sing praise; in your presence, O LORD, I will make music. ² God said, “I will make you wise in the perfect way; when will you come unto me?” David said, “I will walk in the perfection of my heart within my house of instruction.” ³ I will not set upon my heart the word of the wicked man, the ones who do evil; and those who wander from the commandments I hate, they will not follow me. ⁴ Let the twisted heart pass from me; I shall not know the evil impulse. ⁵ He who relates slander against his fellow – him will I overturn; and he who walks with haughty eyes will be stricken with leprosy; with him I will never dwell. ⁶ My eyes are on the honest of the land, to dwell in the precincts of the righteous; he who walks perfect on the way – he shall stand among my ministers. ⁷ He who acts guilefully will not dwell in the midst of my sanctuary; he who speaks lies has no right to stand before my eyes. ⁸ In the age to come, which is likened to the light of morning, I will overturn all the wicked of the earth, to destroy from Jerusalem, the city of the LORD, all those who work deceit.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

King David contemplated the wonders of the LORD through nature. One of the miracles of the LORD is the birth of a baby. This Psalm is a song of inspiration that came to David. It describes how David secluded himself. He hated evil and had a sincere love for strict justice.

Verse one

David calls out to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's love.

I will sing to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's love, and to the Sefirah Gevurah for justice, LORD, I address my song.

Notes of the Psalm

The Scriptures are not afraid to tell stories about the fall of heroes. King David was the most beloved of the Kings of Israel. However, he did commit a couple of sins that the LORD forgave him. Yes, David had flaws, and the Scriptures want us to know that even the best person can fail. David was punished for this act of adultery and murder by the death of the baby that was conceived with Bathsheba. After his repentance, the next child of Bathsheba was Solomon, who followed David as king and built the LORD's Temple. David was told by the LORD that he could not produce the Temple. Instead, David gathered the building materials needed for the project. David wanted the LORD's love and justice to help him rule over the land.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

